

Fundamental philosophical commitments for Top-Level Ontologies

What are their benefits?

OSKAR HOLTZ (GOLDBECK CONSULTING)

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What is an ontology?

Before getting into the benefits from committing to consistent philosophical positions when constructing an ontology, it might be helpful to outline what an ontology is. Broadly, the field of ontology was introduced by Aristotle (although he didn't explicitly call it ontology) as a 'science of being qua being'. But it was dismissed for quite a while in the modern era, mostly by the early analytic and neo-positivistic traditions (see Berto, F. and Plebani, M., 2015. *Ontology and metaontology: A contemporary guide*). Starting with Quine at around the second half of the 20th century, ontology once again became a prominent field of study within philosophy. Quine characterised the task of ontology as writing down a complete catalogue of all the things that exist (for top level ontologies, this will include the relations between entities as well), this view then became the mainstream. So, an ontology gets the catalogue right to the extent that it includes nothing that doesn't exist and doesn't exclude things that do exist (ibid.). Within the field of ontology there are numerous ongoing debates between different schools of thought with different fundamental positions, for example, the debate between those who think abstract objects exist (Platonists) vs those who do not (nominalists).

Top-level ontologies should commit to fundamental positions within the field of ontology and philosophy more broadly. This is important as it ensures logical consistency by providing general rules to be followed. You have to know the rules of the game (or at least state them) in order to successfully play any game, the same is true of ontology or any systematised body of knowledge, moreover, the rules of any game cannot contradict each other for obvious reasons. Thus, there are constraints on which positions are viable.

Potential issues with creating an ontology

It is easy, when creating an ontology (whether explicitly or implicitly) to create an inconsistent schema. To see an example of this, consider the class 'award' as elucidated on Wikidata¹, which classifies it as a subclass of 'recognition', which is itself a subclass of 'acknowledgment' and further 'assertion' which is a subclass of 'speech act'. So, from Wikidata, 'award' is supposedly a subclass of 'speech act', which is clearly not the case (we would then expect to see trophies, cheques, and medals as subclasses of speech acts). This is but a small example of how not providing (and following) general guidelines when building an ontology (the backbone of which is a taxonomy), can lead to inconsistency further down the line. These general guidelines are typically provided by core/fundamental philosophical commitments. One may wonder, however, whether this kind of problem requires a top-level ontology as problem-solver, surely a domain ontology will do just fine?

In the case provided, it is true that a domain ontology could suffice in dealing with these issues, but another elucidating and broader example (borrowed from Vervaeke's (2019) lecture series 'awakening from the meaning crisis') will show that even if the specific domain ontology is logically coherent and consistent, huge problems arise from the inconsistency between different domains. The example comes from within academia and what can be characterised as the 'mind sciences': neuroscience (mind as brain/neural systems), computer science/A.I. (mind as information processing), psychology (mind as behaviour), linguistics (mind as language), anthropology (mind as distributed cognition/culture). The concept 'mind' has become equivocal in these domains. Equivocation leads to confusion because the meaning of concepts has not been adequately 'tracked',

¹ <https://www.wikidata.org/>

and this is precisely what ontology can help deal with, i.e. to keep track of the meaning of concepts. One of the consequences of this equivocation across domains is fragmentation. Each level of understanding of the term 'mind,' each of those disciplines, causally impact and constrain one another. The constant need for hybrids like "psycholinguistics" reveal this fragmentation.

To study any phenomena we need to get different domains (with different perspectives) to integrate in some way. Philosophy can help us achieve this integration, because it is the discipline that has us take conceptual care to try and articulate the meaning of our terms and bridge between different vocabularies, ontologies, methodologies, etc. The case of the cognitive sciences should help us see a parallel issue in the natural sciences (namely, physics, chemistry, and biology), all give descriptions of the world from different perspectives with different conceptual frameworks. So, top-level ontologies can mitigate the issues arising from equivocating terms and concepts by providing clear identity criteria, and likewise can help construct a coherent, logically consistent system of knowledge by providing general rules which constrain the way we define and categorise entities. Top-level ontologies can help avoid the ever-increasing problems of specialisation by integrating different domains.

Fundamental philosophical commitments of EMMO²

As an example, consider the Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology (EMMO) (Ghedini, Friis, Goldbeck, Hashibon, Schmitz, Moruzzi, Zaccarini, and Varzi, (forthcoming). An Introduction to EMMO's Mereological Foundations). EMMO is a top-level ontology designed to cater in particular to natural and materials sciences. It offers well-defined identity criteria as well as a plurality of perspectives. Its core commitments comprise:

- 1) A pragmatic form of ontological reductionism
- 2) Ontological naturalism
- 3) Nominalism

I will briefly outline what these mean and the benefits each bring.

(1) Ontological Reductionism

Ontological reductionism is closely tied to the notion of 'Unity of Science'; the idea is that the various sciences can be unified into a theory of everything. On this view, all theories from the special sciences (those sciences other than fundamental physics), derive from the most fundamental science: 'Unity of science just means that fundamental physics is what everything else is ultimately based on; the higher-level sciences are somehow derivative' (Tahko, 2021. Unity of Science, p.2). Adopting this view in a top-level ontology facilitates interoperability, as it is assumed that all science domains can be reconciled and connected, as they are ultimately investigating the same phenomena at different levels of granularity, despite their semantic pluralism. As Tahko points out, ontological reductionism and semantic reductionism (the view that the semantics of the special sciences can be reduced to the semantics of fundamental science) need not go hand-in-hand, although this has been frequently assumed. EMMO remains neutral with respect to semantic reductionism, and in fact embraces representational pluralism, assuming that the special sciences are as precise as they need

² <https://github.com/emmo-repo/EMMO>

to be in order to achieve specific goals. Representational pluralism is the result of focusing on different parts of the world at different scales with a different conceptual schema. This means that in EMMO, the special sciences can retain all of their semantics, however, it is still assumed that in principle fundamental physics should be able to account for any and all phenomena, as ultimately the entities the special sciences are focused on can be studied in terms of their elementary parts (Ghedini, et al. (forthcoming). *An Introduction to EMMO's Mereo-Causal Foundations*).

More broadly, reductionism assumes that what is essential about some entity is what it shares with other entities, how it's identical with other entities. When a property is in common, the more in common it is the more it is perceived to convey reality. If I drop "lower down" (to a more fundamental level), I get better, more generalised results. This leads to an increase in explanatory and predictive power. So, more real means more intelligible (i.e., explanatory and predictive power), more intelligible means more generalisable – that which is held in common. Reductionism allows us to pick up on what is context independent and thus less contingent. If I take three objects, a key, a glass, and a table, in order to explain each I need to know the properties of each, but reductionism affords a greater capacity for explanation as I can look at how these things are identical, namely, all are made out of matter, and then I need only focus on the properties of matter to explain and predict the behaviour of all three objects (Vervaeke, 2019. *Awakening from the meaning crisis*).

(2) Ontological Naturalism and (3) Nominalism

EMMO embraces an empiricist stance, meaning that in principle, everything that exists can be known via observation, with the further assumption that all observation requires causation. So, causality is fundamental in EMMO, taking the stance that to say anything about entities one has to observe them. Thus, entities which have no causal efficacy are not allowed in EMMO, and (2) ontological naturalism follows (the thesis that there exists only one kind of entity, namely, natural entities). Naturally, nominalism follows from this, abstract objects and sets are not allowed in EMMO, however, the role typically fulfilled by these are instead fulfilled by semiotic objects (e.g., signs, symbols, and icons).

Nominalism and naturalism together ensure parsimony, reality is constituted by one sort of entity – namely, concrete entities. Thus the thesis is modest, operating at the level of particulars and not kinds. It also allows for flexibility of representation, as it is assumed that the carving of reality is done by convenience, with a specific purpose in mind. This ensures that the representations built by the different sciences, and even their sub-disciplines, are on equal footing, as they all have their own purposes in mind when individuating entities. However, in conformity with ontological reductionism, it is assumed that the representations at different levels of granularity have as their truth-makers the very bottom layer of reality, namely, the entities described by elementary physics (Ghedini, et al., (forthcoming). *An Introduction to EMMO's Mereo-Causal Foundations*).

In order to understand the motivations behind nominalism, it may be helpful to consider the adverse position briefly, namely, Platonism. Platonism is the view that universals (or forms/kinds) exist independently of the mind. Universals are general classes which exist over and above the particulars which instantiate any said universals. For example, 'finger' is a universal of which my own particular fingers are instantiations, even though they all differ from one another they are nevertheless fingers. Universals are not concrete entities, they exist outside of the realm of sense perception and so in a sense are speculative entities, we do not have direct access to them. One of the major problems with universals is that upon closer examination they seem to be semantic entities, we can begin to see

this if we look at the previous example of ‘finger’ but instead consider ‘toe’, what makes these universals distinct? Spanish doesn’t even have a word for ‘toe’, instead they say ‘fingers of the feet’ or ‘dedos de los pies’, so, has English discovered a distinct universal, or mistaken a toe as a universal? A plausible answer seems to be that these general terms are simply linguistic artefacts and do not represent universals which exist mind-independently, but rather universals which are mind-dependent. Furthermore, the forms which Plato constantly references do not seem to have any definition, indeed, in his dialogues this is what the main protagonist, Socrates, seems to be constantly driving at, as he repeatedly dismantles any attempts to define a given form (and then refuses to give a definition himself). Furthermore, Antisthenes, a student of Socrates (who was perhaps closer to him than Plato was) explicitly states ‘it is impossible to define the essence’; for applied ontology, this isn’t very helpful, we need to be able to give clear identity criteria (i.e., definitions which are computable) in order to organise the data we collect into a coherent system.

This is a brief overview of the dichotomy, much more could be said, but the nominalist position can be summed up by a problem-solving principle attributed to one of the pioneers of nominalism, namely Ockham’s razor from William of Ockham, which states: do not multiply entities beyond necessity. If we can minimise the entities within an ontology without losing any explanatory and predictive power, then we are compelled to do so. This leads to a big project within the philosophy of science of nominalising science. To do this, the nominalist must do without positing the existence of abstract objects (e.g., numbers, functions, sets, universals etc) and must find a way to account for the success of these ‘entities’ in terms which do not commit one to the existence of these entities in their own right; to see an example of this, see (Field, 1980. Science without Numbers). One of the main motivations for this project, as Field repeatedly makes clear, is that abstract objects do not play the same role within explanations as do concrete objects, ‘electrons are causally relevant to the phenomena they are invoked to explain. But even on the Platonistic assumption that there are numbers, no one thinks that those numbers are causally relevant to the physical phenomena’ and further, that eliminating extrinsic explanation (like numbers) in favour of intrinsic explanation (like the behaviour of particles) will ultimately be more illuminating; ‘more illuminating because the elimination of numbers... helps us to further a plausible methodological principle: the principle that *underlying every good extrinsic explanation there is an intrinsic explanation*’ (ibid., p.43-44). The extrinsic explanation can then be seen as a helpful fiction.

To sum up, nominalism is an attractive stance mainly due to its parsimony, but also because it seems likely that mathematical entities are not indispensable to science unlike theoretical entities (e.g., particles), although they are very helpful. Having a TLO operate at the level of tokens is beneficial as this is ultimately what users deal with in their day-to-day professions. Furthermore, having everything fall under one kind of existence simplifies things a great deal, the Platonist has multiple categories of existence as such, this entails an extra step in categorising entities: is it concrete or abstract? This isn’t the same as asking whether something is a table or a cup, as both share the same *kind* of existence (namely, concrete), rather it is an ontological dualism, there are two separate categories of existence as such. Nominalism, then, is the more pragmatic and frugal choice.

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Bibliography

Berto, F. and Plebani, M., 2015. *Ontology and metaontology: A contemporary guide*. Bloomsbury Publishing.

Field, H.H., 1980. *Science Without Numbers. A defence of Nominalism*. Princeton University Press.

Ghedini, E., Friis, J., Goldbeck, G., Hashibon, A., Schmitz, G., de Baas, A., Moruzzi, S., Zaccarini, F., and Varzi, A., (forthcoming). *An Introduction to EMMO's Mereology-Causal Foundations*

Tahko, T.E., 2021. *Unity of Science*. Cambridge University Press.

Vervaeke, J., 2019. 'Awakening from the meaning crisis':

<<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iu9fa4TkWE0&list=PLND1JCRq8Vuh3f0P5qjrSdb5eC1ZfZwWJ>>